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Mending the broken world, rebuilding the community – on positive biopolitics in digital games

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Abstract:	<p>This article aims to problematize two major paradigms of positive biopolitics in digital games. The study uses biopolitical analysis tools developed within and without game studies, to explore the positive pole of biopolitics, often neglected by critically oriented game studies. The article presents short case studies of simulation strategy games <i>Terra Nil</i> and <i>The Wandering Village</i> that thematically reference positive forms of governance: rebuilding the community, mending the world after catastrophes, and achieving a social, economic, or ecological utopia. Within these games, I searched for representations of positive biopolitics, understood as good community-oriented governance over life. The analyses broaden the understanding of the biopolitical aspects of environmental governmentality in digital games and provide explanations of two modes of realizing the philosophy of care in ecogames.</p>

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49 **Introduction**
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52 This paper draws from biopolitical theory, which problematizes control over individual and
53
54 collective forms of life by providing critique of knowledge structures, institutions, laws and
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56 politics. Applied to game studies, this theory provides insight into how games represent life,
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58 the media specific ways in which games play with control and power structures, and how they
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3 extend the governance mechanisms of contemporary societies. When speaking about games
4 and biopolitics we usually do not expect anything positive (Savaş, 2022). These analyses focus
5 almost exclusively on problematizations of racism (Dyer-Witheford & Peuter, 2009),
6 destruction (Rutheford & Bose, 2013), death (Christiansen, 2014), social control (Kattenberg,
7 2015; Lenkevich, 2021; Piero, 2020), and surveillance (Väliaho, 2014). There are studies on
8 the resistance to the negative aspects of biopolitics (Zhu, 2018, 2023), but no biopolitical game
9 studies seem to focus on positive biopolitics – governance of the population as community
10 building, balancing community and immunity (Esposito, 2012) or positive rethinking of
11 reproduction (Mills, 2011). The biopolitical problematic in general spans between two poles,
12 which Esposito identified as realizing the logic of immunization (or community-immunity
13 dynamic). This logic can be found at the core of various apparatuses of control at the level of
14 the body (immune system) and society (law), that, in order to protect life, have to incorporate
15 negative and dangerous elements in them (the immune system immunizes by incorporating the
16 destructive element, the law immunizes by incorporating violence). Therefore, the positive
17 biopolitics invested in the protection of life, betterment of living conditions, and individuation,
18 is always already using mechanisms of immunization, which can grow to a point at which that
19 positive biopolitics breaks, and becomes a destructive force of death – thanatopolitics (Esposito,
20 2017, pp. 58-60). Esposito exemplifies such a shift with the Nazi obsession with the
21 medicalization of life and the health of the German body, which transforms life protection into
22 the production of death (Esposito, 2008, p. 115). Therefore, This study will focus on the analysis
23 and interpretation of games that can be seen as promoting positive modes of governance, or at
24 least try to do so in a meaningful and productive way. Out of many games focusing on
25 governance, ~~be looking at titles such as~~ *Terra Nil* (Free Lives, 2023) and *The Wandering Village*
26 (Stray Fawn Studio, 2022) come to mind as first-hand examples of a trend in rethinking positive
27 aspects or vectors of game biopolitics. I decided to examine these specific titles because of their
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3 unique and original engagement with environmental issues. The study focuses on simulation
4 games where governance is inscribed in the “god game” perspective: top-down view on the
5 map; interfaces: surveillance of various economic, ecological, and social factors; and
6 mechanics: decision-making, map management, and modeling of behavior, system, social,
7 economic feedback loops (Giddings, 2016, pp. 261–264). These games often fall into the
8 category of strategy games, due to their use of fog of war, and wargame strategy gameplay
9 (Dor, 2016, p. 276), thus for this study I will not differentiate between simulation and strategy
10 games, as their common dependencies can be traced to trade and war games and their imperial
11 agendas (Flanagan & Jakobsson, 2023, p. 77).
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24 The titular concepts of mending and rebuilding correspond to the general trend seen in
25 ecocritical simulation and strategy games, where positive biopolitics is a choice or reaction to
26 a catastrophic event. On the one hand, these concepts bring philosophical reflection on waste,
27 with its unique insights into the meanings that are produced by broken things when they become
28 broken. Beyond an archeological exploration of what things mediate about the past, this
29 reflection is based on the idea that broken tools allow us to understand the ‘true’ meanings of
30 things, oftentimes taken for granted or invisible at the time of their use, in their pristine
31 condition (Viney, 2014). On the other hand, mending and rebuilding tie the community–
32 immunity dynamic (Esposito, 2012) to the discussions about the ways to deal with the aftermath
33 of the anthropogenic calamities. This can be seen in games that titles focusing focus on survival,
34 such as *Surviving Mars* (Abstraction Games, 2021), *Surviving the Aftermath* (Iceflake Studios,
35 2021), *Frostpunk* (11 bit studios, 2018), *The Wandering Village* (Stray Fawn Studio, 2022), to
36 name a few. The idea of survival can be seen as the keyword for introducing the concept of the
37 state of exception into the game representations and mechanics. Originally defined by Carl
38 Schmitt in his *Political Theology* the state of exception is the “unlimited authority, which means
39 the suspension of the entire existing order” (Schmitt, 2008, p. 12). The sovereignty of the player
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3 in simulation and strategy games is established within a certain extradiegetic order. Still, at the
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5 same time, the games can narratively put forward the idea that the diegetic order is – from a
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7 legal point of view – concurrent with the state of exception. Following Schmitt’s understanding,
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9 power is dependent on decision-making, which is why the state of exception seems such an
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11 attractive narrative framework for establishing and justifying the absolute sovereignty of the
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13 player. The sovereignty defined here is of course of the negative kind, understood as the power
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15 to kill. As Nicole Shukin explains, it is the non-incriminatory character of killing that in this
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17 case applies to all things under such power: “Indeed, the power to reduce humans to the bare
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19 life of their species body arguably presupposes the prior power to suspend other species in a
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21 state of exception within which they can be noncriminally put to death.” (Shukin, 2009, p. 10).
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23 Achille Mbembe further delves into the discussions about the state of exception, and another,
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25 important category for the strategy and simulation games – the state of siege. The researcher
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27 writes:
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34 “The state of siege is itself a military institution. It allows for a modality of killing that does not
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36 distinguish between the external and the internal enemy. Entire populations are the target of the
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38 sovereign. Besieged villages and towns are sealed off and isolated from the world. Daily life is
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40 militarized. Local military commanders have the discretionary freedom to decide whom to
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42 shoot and when. Movement between the territorial cells requires formal permits. Local civil
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44 institutions are systematically destroyed. The besieged population is deprived of their means of
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46 income. Invisible killing is added to outright executions.” (Mbembe, 2020, pp. 82–83)
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51 The simulation and strategy games mentioned above use both the state of exception and the
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53 state of siege to convey a sense of urgency, and isolation, and work with establishing a
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55 procedural rhetoric of boundaries. This rhetoric boils down to binary decision-making strategies
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57 concerning people (accepting or rejecting migrants), environment (dividing healthy from
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59 unhealthy land), and hygiene (identifying and curing ailments). What interests me in this article
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3 is the representation of the positive aspects of these decisions and their diegetic legitimation.

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5 That is why I limited its scope in a twofold way. Firstly, the narrative framework of the state of
6
7 exception narrows down the possible game choices. Secondly, the choice of simulation and
8
9 strategy games limits the scope of the study to the games focusing on governance.

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12 I hypothesize that positive biopolitics is the unexplored aspect of the problematization of care
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14 in games (Ruberg & Scully-Blaker, 2021), and an interesting approach to fostering discussions
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16 on ~~when tackling solutions to~~ the contemporary game representations of the climate crisis
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18 (Medrala, 2020; Wu & Lee, 2015), framed as a state of exception or state of siege due to the
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20 contemporary disastrous effects of the Anthropocene (Lewis & Maslin, 2015). This hypothesis
21
22 is grounded in Boris Groys' identification of philosophy of care as a paradigm of biopolitical
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24 state: "By taking care of its whole population the biopolitical state treats everybody as sick and
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26 distributes care according to the system of hierarchies and ranks that define the place of
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28 individual symbolic bodies." (Groys, 2022, 23).

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Problematizing positive biopolitics in simulation and strategy games, or as Tomasz Majkowski calls these, "game models" (Majkowski, 2019) is an important task for a variety of reasons. First of all, positive biopolitics – as seen from the reflection on the state of exception – seldom functions without the negative horizon. Researching representations of different dispositives used to better the society or the world is thus an exploration of how they convey the balance between positive and negative forms of governance. This continues the critical efforts to understand how games offer alternatives to the forms identified as imperial, and broadly related to the ideological narratives produced within the current social, political, and economic imaginary (Dyer-Witheford & Peuter, 2009). Secondly, because games simplify complex processes to simulate, model, and render them visible, they offer a unique way of understanding and interpreting biopolitical problems. Exploring how games mediate problems and solutions concerning governmentality helps us understand their participation in cultural and artistic

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3 debates on human agency and power in the wake of a state of exception, and ecological crisis.
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5 Lastly, it is also pleasurable to seek the truth that game developers aim to convey using games
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7 as critical devices.
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10 11 12 13 **Positive biopolitics and reflexivity** 14

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19 The concept of positive biopolitics has been problematized from different angles. The newest
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21 reflection by Sergei Prozorov focuses on the “subjectivation of beings in resistance to and
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23 confrontation with the apparatuses of governing life” (Prozorov, 2021, p. 147), and is a direct
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25 continuation of Foucault’s reflection on the practice of truth-telling (*parrhesia*), and the
26
27 relationship between veridiction and techniques of governmentality, as opposed to the practice
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29 of saying anything (Foucault, 2011, pp. 8–10). Foucault explains that this practice of parrhesia,
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31 in the most positive sense, means a commitment to telling the whole truth without withholding
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33 anything. This is done under the condition that the one assuming the parrhesiast role believes
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35 in what they are saying and that their truth-saying challenges the relationship between them and
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37 their interlocutors (Foucault, 2011, p. 11). With this practice in mind, positive biopolitics is
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39 understood as literally “putting one’s life at stake for truth” (Prozorov, 2021, p. 149). This ties
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41 to Prozorov’s work on biopolitics and democracy, where democratic biopolitics is defined as a
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43 system in which the contingency of different forms of life practice is enjoyable (Prozorov, 2019,
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45 pp. 167–172). In short, Prozorov argues that democracy and biopolitics fail if they become
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47 disjointed, if democracy ceases to be about life, or in close relation to it, or if there is no
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49 contingency and enjoyment in a political regime. Democracy as a form of positive biopolitics
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51 is thus all about experiencing life as potentiality and freedom, where the contingency of life
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53 forms is legitimized and enjoyable. He writes: “There is pleasure in the diversity and pluralism
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3 of forms of life only when these forms are not assigned to one as determinate identities but
4 remain available as potentialities to adopt, uphold or abandon, be captivated by or bored with”.
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6 (Prozorov, 2019, p. 170).
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10 Simply put, the pleasure of self-forming, exploring, and enjoying the contingency of life forms
11 without stressing proper, normal, or necessary ones would be the most important and defining
12 aspect of positive biopolitics in democracy. From a game studies perspective, Feng Zhu
13 developed a similar approach considering player reflexivity as a practice of resistance and self-
14 forming through game expertise, referencing the works of Foucault (Zhu, 2018, p. 77, 2023,
15 41, 46-47). Feng Zhu stresses three assumptions for considering gaming practices as work on
16 the self: first, conscious setting of one’s goals instead of external determination; second, slow
17 transformation, via the player’s work on their being; and third, a combination of similar
18 practices which reinforce the transformative power of games (Zhu, 2018, p. 99). Therefore,
19 where Prozorov underlines practicing democracy and veridiction, Zhu stresses the resistance to
20 external determinants and conscious self-formation due to reflexivity. The affirmative
21 biopolitics in games would therefore be identifiable as a tension between practicing democratic
22 enjoyment of games on one hand, and self-reflexively resisting overdetermination of gaming
23 patterns (and neoliberal ideology) on the other. Affirmative game biopolitics would therefore
24 acknowledge that gaming practices are forms of life, and gaming can be understood as one of
25 the possible contingent forms of life in a democracy, a form of life endangered by its neoliberal
26 captivation and governance (Lassila, 2022, pp. 18–20).
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50 Games are also an important form within democracy, as they function as its critical
51 commentary, and as media forms they extend its ideas and stage renegotiations of their values,
52 offering both alternatives and ideological ossifications. In this sense games’ proximity to
53 biopolitics makes them important testbeds for speaking truth to power, albeit with only the
54 personal experiences at stake, but still an invaluable space of possibilities for the self (Gualeni
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3 & Vella, 2020, p. 114). When Apperley and Clemens analyzed the avatar as a disciplinary
4 apparatus (Apperley & Clemens, 2016, pp. 120–121), they opened up a biopolitically oriented
5 critical inquiry into a tool for controlling the players by monitoring their progress, teaching
6 them movement patterns, or putting them in a position of power and privilege (Wildt, Apperley,
7 Clemens, Fordyce, & Mukherjee, 2020, p. 973). However, this usually suspect form of control
8 can also be seen as one of the forms of life produced to take pleasure in democratic biopolitics.
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10 As Prozorov states: “The enjoyment of democracy is nothing other than the pleasure of giving
11 form to one’s being. Thus, biopolitical democracy is not merely sustainable but is in fact
12 strengthened, quite literally *reinvigorated* by its translation into concrete forms of life”.
13 (Prozorov, 2019, p. 18). To put this in use and translate onto games as simply as possible:
14 avatars are forms of life in democratic biopolitics. Through avatars, democratic biopolitics
15 produces devices for the pleasure of self-reflexivity coming from pluralism and contingency on
16 one hand, and internal and external systemic governance on the other. However, the avatar is a
17 form of life in democracy regardless of its use, and as such can be seen as a marker of
18 democratic biopolitics, because it is a life form mirroring the very democratic process of self-
19 forming, indeterminacy, and potentialities. Control over the process of avatarisation would
20 therefore be another crucial factor in determining the state of democratic biopolitics, and the
21 production of avatars could be seen as expanding or contracting the democratic sphere of
22 available potential and contingent life forms. The most negative forms of this process,
23 questioning its democratic claims, have been identified by Nakamura as racism, orientalization,
24 identity tourism, and “default whiteness”, questioning the racial normalization in the name of
25 “cybersocial hygiene” (Nakamura, 2013, pp. 39–47). Contrary to these negative processes,
26 positive biopolitics can be realized with the use of avatars as devices of veridiction, of truth-
27 telling as a practice, and as devices for player self-reflexivity to resist governance, or as
28 Nakamura calls it, “jamming the ideology machine” (Nakamura, 2013, p. 49). The two analyzed
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3 games operate with a top-down, strategic perspective, so the players are not given control over
4 an avatar body, as they operate within the world using a simple cursor. However, such
5 situatedness puts them in a sovereign position of power, and in that regard plays with the
6 imaginary collectivist avatar, leader, and decision-maker, which Daniel Kromand identified as
7 atypical avatars (Kromand, 2007, p. 405). Such avatarisation renders governance at the
8 executive level of the power structure, allowing players to engage with the form of life related
9 to pure decision-making and reflect on its pleasures, burdens, and challenges.

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11 With this section, I reconstructed the general linkages between previous game studies on self-
12 reflexivity and avatars as important insights into the understanding of positive biopolitics at the
13 level of player interaction with the game, namely, enjoying the freedom of play as a democratic
14 practice, truth-telling, and resistance to normalization. These values formulate the core of an
15 affirmative type of biopolitical engagement with the game, both for players and artists designing
16 them it.

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18 The subsequent section will focus on the relationship between positive biopolitics and games
19 of governance, where mending the broken world is conveyed through top-down strategic
20 modeling or simulation of digital life, demography, and population dynamics. Thus, from the
21 general discussion of self-reflexivity, it is now time to address the concept of care, which
22 expands the discussion of positive biopolitics to encompass matters of the environment,
23 sustainability, and ecocriticism.

24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 **Positive biopolitics and care**

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57 On the surface, positive biopolitics in simulation games seems easier to identify than in other
58 game types. However, the ideas of veridiction or enjoyment with democracy fall short of
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3 capturing the way governance is represented in strategy and simulation games regarding
4 positive biopolitics. The crucial aspect of governance games is that they allow players to
5 experience both controlling how people act on beliefs (conducting themselves), and governing
6 through the conduct of conduct: setting up rules and beliefs about governmentality itself.
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8 Foucault explicitly combines this with the care for oneself and the care for others (Foucault
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10 2011, pp. 159-160). What I am trying to say is that positive biopolitics should be conceptualized
11 differently concerning game models – the “games which expose the rules governing the world
12 by focusing on building models of reality and its systems” (Majkowski, 2019, p. 306).
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22 One of the most interesting tropes of positive biopolitics in games is related to the games of
23 care. As shown by Bonnie Ruberg and Rainforest Scully-Blaker care can be identified as a core
24 concept in a wide array of products from virtual pet simulators, to RTS, life sims, and
25 MMORPG's (Ruberg & Scully-Blaker, 2021, p. 657), and it can function at different levels of
26 engagement, from in-game activities, through interpersonal player relations to community-
27 developer care (Ruberg & Scully-Blaker, 2021, p. 669). However, where they explore the topic
28 of care from a feminist and intersectional perspective, questioning the politics of care in the
29 context of patriarchy and global capitalism (Ruberg & Scully-Blaker, 2021, pp. 658–659), my
30 perspective is tailored to search for biopolitical markers related to positive biopolitics (for
31 example, quality of life indicators for governed populace) as a general theoretical framework.
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33 The positive analyses of care in Ruberg's and Scully-Blaker's case studies reveal ambivalences
34 coming from the intertwining of neoliberal rhetoric of self-care and communal care (Ruberg
35 & Scully-Blaker, 2021, p. 662), misusing empathy in game design causing “re-marginalization
36 of those they seek to support” (Ruberg & Scully-Blaker, 2021, p. 664), or critical bifurcations
37 between community care for game characters and concern for labor politics of the studio
38 (Ruberg & Scully-Blaker, 2021, pp. 667–668). From the perspective of critically oriented
39 analyses of biopolitics, these ambivalences can be seen as specific realizations of the
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3 immunization paradigm, which Roberto Esposito problematizes, referencing the dynamic
4 between immunity and community. This dynamic is achieved by including in the community
5 that which endangers it (Esposito, 2017, pp. 13–15), including in the life that which negates it:
6
7 “To escape from the extreme risk of annihilation, life must take inside itself a fragment of the
8 nothingness that threatens it from outside. It must partially and preventively incorporate what
9 negates it”. (Esposito, 2017, p. 65). With this theorization, I would like to continue analyzing
10 the positive biopolitics in game models along the lines of this preventative incorporation, as
11 this seems more productive than a critique that will inevitably conclude that games would be
12 better without neoliberal policies installed in their every nook and cranny. I’m therefore more
13 interested in how game models preventively incorporate neoliberalism, dismantling it and
14 putting it in the service of positive biopolitics.
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29 Another angle of approach to the problem of positive biopolitics and care is related to such
30 concepts as waste, repair, and maintenance (Viney, 2014), which have been deployed to
31 describe the alternative order to capitalist production and reproduction of capital (Corwin &
32 Gidwani, 2021, pp. 4–6). In this sense, the positive aspects of biopolitics can be seen in care as
33 the agency and drive to prolong the usefulness of things through repair, reuse, and recycling
34 practices. Viney theorizes that “waste objects (which connote a time that is tardy, used up or
35 ‘past it’) serve to reinforce a temporal difference that means objects structure time, marking the
36 beginning of a narrative and the conclusion to that narrative” (Viney, 2014, p. 66), so their
37 archeological exploration is a reconstruction of the events that they mark and mediate. Caring,
38 repairing, recycling, and mending, in the case of positive biopolitics, play critical roles in
39 narrating the process of things becoming broken, thus visualizing the thanatopolitical aspects
40 of the past. Caring for the broken objects would therefore translate into a form of biopolitical
41 maintenance, evoking discourses of sustainability, recycling, and repair, juxtaposed to the idea
42 of one-time use, acceleration of consumerism, and waste generation.
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3 The last strand in problematizing positive biopolitics and care can be traced to the broader
4 reflection on the ecologies of media, which recognize and acknowledge the cultural impact of
5 popular media on the human-environment relationship, because they enable debates on how
6 humans should inhabit the world (Rust, Monani & Cubitt 2016, pp. 5-6). This perspective
7 analyzes games as powerful media due to their ability to blend fact and fiction in a convincing
8 way, thus offering both oversimplifications and green washings (Clark, 2016, 189-191), as well
9 as “vast ecocritical potential” (Woolbright & Oliveira, 2016, 209) to be explored for the cause
10 of fostering care for the environment. For example, following Donna Haraway’s theory of
11 rethinking and practicing making kin (Haraway, 2016), Melissa Bianchi argues that games
12 provide complex assemblages of mechanics and representations, allowing players to enact
13 transformative multispecies relationships based on care (Bianchi, 2017, pp. 140-143). Other
14 positive effects of games have been identified by Lawrence May and Ben Hall as resonance
15 and amplification of engagement with ecological thought (May & Hall, 2024), which they
16 position next to dissonance, abjection, and weirdness experienced by players in relation to
17 ecocritical themes. Bianchi also defined a mode of engagement with games called ecoplay,
18 which considers the ecological situatedness of play within broader ecosystems, in the analysis
19 of their meaning-making strategies (Bianchi, 2020, p. 19). Ecogame and ecomedia theorists
20 thus provide ample critical input on how games in general and serious games in particular are
21 designed with consideration of value systems they represent, criticize, and support by
22 “conscientious designers” (Flanagan & Nissenbaum, 2014, p. 12). Engagement with the themes
23 of environmental governance from the perspective of positive biopolitics is also a way of
24 providing critical feedback on the way they mediate their ecocritical agendas. The following
25 case studies depict how *Terra Nil* and *The Wandering Village* differ in their exposition of
26 ecocritical governance.
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Identifying positive biopolitics in governance games

The analysis in this section is based on the framework for identifying biopolitical markers, game elements signifying: veillance, thanatopolitics, biopower, and immunity/community (Kłosiński 2024, pp. 4-5). These markers are presented using concept cluster maps that reference four game ontological layers (communicational, structural, mental and physical) and their sublayers described by Aarseth and Grabarczyk in their meta-ontological model (Aarseth & Grabarczyk, 2018, p. 7). To present markers of positive biopolitics, I decided to analyze two game models that both evoke the concept of care in a very original way and contextualize it as part of ecocritical game design. *Terra Nil* and *The Wandering Village* are independent productions focusing on strategic gameplay, but their overarching narrative theme differs. *Terra Nil* focuses on recovering and mending of the biosphere and environment destroyed by anthropogenic activity, where the players aim to rejuvenate the climate affordances of the land so that its “original” and “natural” inhabitants (flora and fauna) can be observed. The players are put in the position of environmental strategists, who work with limited resources to complete environmental quests. *The Wandering Village* is a city-builder survival game focusing on building a narrative about a village atop a humongous creature called Onbu in a post-apocalyptic world where a toxic environment endangers both the village and its host. The players are put in the position of governors, village planners, and negotiators of a symbiotic relationship between the singularity of Onbu’s being and the community. Caring for the creature and guiding it through the toxic environment is as important as caring for the villagers and meeting their needs. This short synopsis of the game's narrative already presents a handful of biopolitical markers. For the sake of clarity, I have presented these in the form of concept maps below:

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3 [Insert Figure 1. Map of biopolitical markers in *Terra Nil*]
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9 [Insert Figure 2. Map of biopolitical markers in *The Wandering Village*]
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12 Mapping of biopolitical markers in both games revealed significant differences in their
13 conceptualization of positive biopolitics. Out of the two games, *Terra Nil* identified as a
14 “reverse city builder” (Beke, Raessens, & Werning, 2024, p. 11) operates almost exclusively
15 with biopolitical markers associated with presentational, mechanical, semantic, and interface
16 sublayers of the game ontology (Aarseth & Grabarczyk, 2018), producing a conceptual and
17 phenomenal model of caring for the planet. An important, yet underrepresented aspect of the
18 game is its social layer, where it explicitly underlies the producer’s agenda related to the
19 Endangered Wildlife Trust initiative. The positive biopolitics can be seen in the semantics of
20 “restoration”, “regeneration”, and “reclamation”, intertwined with procedural rhetoric and
21 mechanics of utilizing scarce resources to reintroduce “original” and “natural” fauna and flora
22 to each of the planetary regions. This procedure has been quantified and presented using
23 economic signifiers of progress: percentages, completion checkboxes, quest lists, and scales
24 depicting milestones of environmental progress. All game buildings cost internal currency
25 represented as green leaves, which are awarded for successful and economical usage of
26 available buildings and facilities. After the biome is reclaimed and the local climate is restarted,
27 the players are tasked with the reclamation of assets, and the economy game is played in reverse
28 – this time to clean up the messy ecological industry used to govern the barren wasteland and
29 regenerate it into a lush and life-sparkling green utopia (Farca, 2019, 2024, p. 254). Thus, the
30 presentational layer combines simulation and representation of both climate and weather,
31 depicting the “factors and phenomena” (Möring & Schneider, 2024, pp. 203–205). Thus, the
32 positive biopolitics in *Terra Nil* is produced along the lines of limited, pragmatic, and
33 economized governance over the territory and its environment. The positive aspect comes from
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3 the set goal: restoration of life and politics of care for the planet, as well as from the procedurally
4 deployed rhetoric of degrowth (Navarro-Remesal, 2019, p. 17) combined with a
5 straightforward depiction of naïve, calculable, big data-based belief in the human-orchestrated
6 return of nature (Chang, 2019, pp. 91–95). Here is where positive biopolitics is best seen in the
7 form of a set of measurements, handbooks, and dispositives, which serve as assemblages of
8 power and knowledge to recover what was lost. The biopolitical governance in *Terra Nil* is
9 positive in its radically twisted way of seeing the end of the Anthropocene as the last gesture of
10 anthropogenic control and governance. The positive biopolitics is based here on the hidden
11 knowledge about the normative basis for the planet's reconstruction, combined with an
12 underlying assumption that the post-human sovereign decision saves the environment, climate,
13 and life. Without the player's agency, there is only wasteland. The major positive biopolitical
14 markers in *Terra Nil* are thus as follows. The game represents life as vitality, the object of
15 biological science, and an attribute, all dependent on a set of normalized and manipulable
16 parameters such as temperature, pollution, and humidity, and presents it to players through a
17 lens of artistic exposition akin to a wildlife reserve with a strong contrast to the wasteland, filled
18 with anthropogenic ruins. The most numerous biopolitical markers are found in the
19 presentational and economic layers, as the game procedurally justifies player agency with
20 colorful depictions of successful climate changes and progress tracker rewards (green leaves).
21 The justification for game checklists and quests is presented in the semantic layer as fueled by
22 a self-explanatory drive to recovery of biomes. We are also given a handful of tools to govern
23 life, thus a prevalence of mechanical markers of biopolitics. All of those are automated
24 buildings that produce or manipulate concrete, climate, and environmental factors. The last
25 building available to players is the observatory, the only explicit invigilation structure, ~~that~~
26 which allows players to identify returning wildlife species. Thinking about the paradigmatic
27 structures as sets of biopolitical markers deployed by *Terra Nil*, we can see that the player
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3 agency focuses on biopolitical care for a dead world, and its immunization by transforming
4 human waste into livable space. We are therefore agents of biopolitics combatting the effects
5 of anthropogenic thanatopolitical disaster.
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10 A different map of biopolitical markers is revealed in the analysis of *The Wandering Village*, a
11 survival city-builder game, identified as an ecogame about symbiosis simulating environmental
12 challenges (Beke et al., 2024, p. 10). The dominant markers in this title can be found in the
13 mechanical, semantic, and presentational sublayers, which combine into a convincing model of
14 symbiosis between the titular village and Onbu. The presentational markers related to
15 thanatopolitics can mostly be found in the deadly representations of the environment
16 surrounding Onbu – poisonous forests, toxic wastelands, and dangerous climate anomalies, but
17 they are also identifiable in the village view, on top of the creature – as toxic spores infesting
18 its back, and visualizations of villager poisoning. The semantic aspect of thanatopolitics can be
19 traced in the descriptions of the mechanics of buildings that extract Onbu’s blood at the cost of
20 its health and its trust in the village, with one significant exception – one service in the
21 technology tree opens up a mechanics of “Placebo”, with a negative effect of 5% instant death
22 chance for the villager receiving this “treatment”. The thanatopolitical markers in the majority
23 are related to the dangers the players work to mitigate, and they are therefore vital to the
24 legitimization of positive biopolitical solutions the game offers. The thanatopolitical semantics
25 of poisoning combines with the community and immunity markers related to representations of
26 communal buildings, and mechanics of Onbu trust on the one hand and community happiness
27 on the other hand, depicted using a set of icons and scales. Again, the markers of community
28 tie into the overarching semantic of care for a life defined on two levels: as the demography,
29 vitality, and well-being of singular villagers, and as the vitality of Onbu. However, the concept
30 of life is presented differently (Mills, 2018, pp. 4–5), for villagers and Onbu. They both possess
31 life as an attribute, vitality, and an object of biological science, but Onbu’s life is not a collective
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3 form of life. In short, the game puts forward the idea that the life of a singular villager is less
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5 important than the life of Onbu, as the communal and demographic economy depends on a
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7 singular life form of the giant creature, however, the creature depends on the overall health of
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9 the community, not particularly on any of its individuals. The relationship between the village
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11 and Onbu's life is built on the mechanics of care. The markers of positive biopolitics and
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13 immunity found at the semantic, mechanics, and economy sublayers concern immunizing Onbu
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15 against parasites, feeding it, and caring for its physiology (excrement and sleep control). This
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17 is achieved by building community with the creature represented in the mechanics and economy
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19 of trust, achieved by researching new ways of caring for and controlling Onbu. The creature is
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21 represented as unaware of the harmful effects of the environment it strolls through, thus
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23 requiring sovereign decision-making and helpful guidance from the villagers. This is where
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25 positive biopolitics can turn into an exploitative endeavor coming close to falling into
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27 thanatopolitics, as the players can research apparatuses (buildings and procedures) that literally
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29 suck the blood out of Onbu, turning the village into a more parasitic community. The model of
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31 symbiosis with Onbu does not fulfill the criteria for the understanding of symbiosis in digital
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33 games proposed by Joost Raessens:
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43 “It is a form of transformative play characterized primarily by mimicry (simulation), where
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45 participants step into the shoes of a symbiotic life form, or “play at being symbionts,” wearing
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47 VR headsets and suits as their costumes or role-playing attributes, in the imagined setting of
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49 the Chthulucene”. (Raessens, 2024, p. 375).
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56 However, *The Wandering Village* achieves something else. It is a representation of symbiosis
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58 along the lines of positive biopolitics, but with significant ambivalence at the core of its
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3 message. This ambivalence can be seen in the structure of markers, where care is mixed with
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5 discipline and control. In this sense, *The Wandering Village* constructs the vision of positive
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7 biopolitics as dependent on circumstances, and immunity-community decisions, always already
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9 carrying the danger of falling into thanatopolitics. The paradigm in this game is construed
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11 around the idea of immunizing the village and Onbu from the dangers that come from the
12
13 outside, the poisoned world. We are the agents of biopolitics dependent on economic and
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15 statistical invigilation apparatuses presented as immediate information about the needs of the
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17 population and Onbu, to be fulfilled in the interest of hygiene, vitality, and health. The
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19 immunity-community dynamic defines the gameplay on all levels. The village grows by
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21 incorporating survivors from the outside world, and the community immunizes Onbu from
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23 parasites.
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32 **Conclusion. Two paradigms of positive biopolitics**

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38 These two case studies show major differences in the paradigmatic structure of representations
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40 of positive biopolitics. *Terra Nil* presents positive biopolitics as a realization of mending
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42 practices through a dominant exposition of markers of biopolitics. *The Wandering Village* also
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44 develops its vision of positive biopolitics through a dominant use of markers of biopolitics, it,
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46 ~~however,~~ does this too, but it leverages these with equal measure of markers of thanatopolitics
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48 and immunity/community. This mixture of biopolitical markers causes *The Wandering Village*
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50 to present positive biopolitics as an ambivalent form of life (symbiosis), rather than a
51
52 biopolitical necessity driven by scientific statistics in the case of *Terra Nil*. This also shows
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54 how the concept of mending plays a pivotal role in producing a vector for biopolitical agency.
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56 In both cases, mending refers to the concept of care. It is however realized differently. *Terra*
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3 *Nil* produces a post-communal perspective, where positive biopolitics comes from governance
4 for the other – for the planet, ecosystem, and life as the vitality and object of biological science
5 which returns thanks to the human agency. This type of mending the broken world assumes that
6 one knows *how* the world *should work and look like*, and *how* to make it *look and work as it*
7 *should*. In this sense, players are put in the position of governance, where they follow the
8 conduct (Lassila, 2022, pp. 18–20) designed somewhere else, their role is to follow and realize
9 dispositives already defining the ideal state of things.

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20 In *The Wandering Village*, the concept of mending is realized through a different biopolitical
21 lens. Players do not mend the broken world, they are agents of immunization and
22 communization, their role being the governance over the conduct of conduct. Their decision
23 shapes the community-immunity dynamic between villagers, Onbu, and the world in a state of
24 exception. The game problematizes care as a constant struggle between positive biopolitics and
25 invigilation and biopower, with a curious aspect of thanatopolitics always lurking in the
26 shadows as an economic, pragmatic, and seductive option to use. With every step towards
27 building a more prosperous village, more dispositives of power over Onbu can be researched
28 and implemented. The community is always already in danger of destroying its real, living host-
29 world. In this case, mending the broken world assumes that one *struggles with power*, and
30 *decides* on the *form of life and community* that *might* sustain different lives and their
31 relationship.

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48 Having analyzed and described the different paradigms of positive biopolitics in *Terra Nil* and
49 *The Wandering Village*, I would like to return to my initial claim that veridiction is complicated
50 in game models as opposed to game novels in regards to Prozorov's idea about democracy
51 being closely tied to the contingency of different life forms and joy coming from this
52 abundance. I assumed that democratic biopolitics finds its extension in games and gaming
53 culture because of avatarisation, which can be seen as a process of producing and experimenting

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3 *with* representations and models of contingent forms of life. With the governance games, this
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5 contingency differs slightly in the sense that we focus on influencing the conditions *for* the
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7 forms of life. Game models allow us to work with positive biopolitics at both levels of conduct.
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10 At the most basic level, the conduct of positive biopolitics is seen in *Terra Nil* in the form of
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12 the power of knowledge, which guides our efforts – we know the optimal parameters and govern
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14 to meet them. At the more advanced level of the “conduct of conduct” of positive biopolitics in
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16 *The Wandering Village*, we decide what the final shape the biopolitics will take – positive or
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18 parasitic.
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22 The initial questions regarding how positive biopolitics is realized in games: ‘what is its relation
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24 to care?’, and ‘what are its paradigms?’ have at least partially been answered. First, positive
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26 biopolitics is realized using games as an extension of the contingency of life forms in
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28 democracy via the process of avatarisation. Second, it is realized using games as vehicles for
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30 transformative, ecological, and ecocritical messages of care. Third, it is realized within games,
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32 as a representation of that care via mechanisms related to community and immunity dynamics,
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34 hygiene, and symbiosis. Defining the notion itself is more problematic, as the framework within
35
36 which positive biopolitics is possible is always marked with ambivalence coming from the
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38 shadow cast by control assumptions underlying its deployment. In democratic avatarisation,
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40 there is the danger of identity tourism and racial defaulting. In the politics of care, there is the
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42 risk of re-marginalisation and desubjectivation. In *Terra Nil*, this ambivalence is produced by
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44 the presumption of human agency as the necessary sovereign and deciding factor in climate
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46 rejuvenation. In *The Wandering Village*, it is deployed in the presumption that Onbu itself needs
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48 exterior control to survive. Both titles cover a very important topic of dealing with the calamity,
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50 which mirrors the contemporary debates about the anthropogenic impact on the planet Earth. If
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52 read as commentaries of the current climate crisis they paint an interesting picture of
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54 anthropocentrism. *Terra Nil* seems to tell us that we can fix things with technological
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3 dependence, but that we have to go leave if our struggles are to succeed and last, a rather
4 disheartening, but reflexive and thought-provoking rhetoric. *The Wandering Village* quite
5 literally makes us “stay with the trouble” (Haraway, 2016, p. 114), meaning that it puts pressure
6 on player’s sense of responsibility and decision making, to convince them that living with Onbu,
7 as our companion, is a challenge necessary for survival, and survival is a manner of being with
8 others. While *Terra Nil* promises and delivers on the idea that players buying the game do
9 impact the well-being of wildlife in Africa, *The Wandering Village* makes no such claims,
10 leaving players to follow ideas and learn from its procedural rhetoric.
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22 The results of both case studies can be extrapolated onto other games. The representational
23 patterns found in *Terra Nil* and *The Wandering Village* suggest two optional realizations of
24 positive biopolitics. The first could be called mandatory or imposed positivity, as games falling
25 into this paradigm do not offer any play with the ‘conduct of conduct’. Namely, the only way
26 to act in these games is to realize a positive life governance scenario according to set parameters.
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The second realization of positive biopolitics could be called optional or recommended
positivity because games from this paradigm play with the ‘conduct of conduct’ by offering a
suggested positive way of governing life, but also enable significant divergencies from this
model, or even play with negative biopolitical scenarios. It is worth noting that positive
biopolitics can be found as representations or procedural rhetoric in many game titles from all
possible genres, but only a critical evaluation of the game’s saturation with biopolitical
signifiers gives us a deeper understanding of what kind of positive biopolitics the game puts
forward.

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[Figure 1.] Map of biopolitical markers in *Terra Nil*

[Figure 2.] Map of biopolitical markers in *The Wandering Village*

